

"ON THE THRESHOLD OF BEING LOST: AN ECOCRITICAL READING OF DEFOE'S ROBINSON CRUSOE"

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Abstract

Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* (1719) has traditionally been regarded as a foundational English novel concerned with adventure, individualism, capitalism and colonialism. However, ecocriticism provides a critical framework for understanding Crusoe as a text deeply engaged with human and nonhuman relations. Ecocriticism interrogates literary depictions of nature, examines anthropocentric assumptions, and appraises how narratives reflect environmental values and crises. This paper offers an ecocritical examination of Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* (1719), analyzing how Crusoe's relationship with the natural world reflects early modern anthropocentrism and foreshadows ecological and colonial imperatives in Western literature. Through an ecocritical lens informed by foundational theory and recent scholarship, Crusoe's survival narrative reveals both the tensions and paradoxes of human-nature relations. The analysis highlights Crusoe's domination over and eventual complex entanglement with the nonhuman environment on the island, demonstrating that Defoe's narrative can be read as an early commentary on ecological consciousness.

Introduction

Looking at the role of man in society, it is often discovered that man is not only in conflict with himself but also with other nonhuman factors around him, thereby foregrounding place as a vital component of literature. For literature to retain its relevance in all human endeavors, it must pay more attention to the effects of man's activities on his environment.

The negative effects of man's activities on the environment have prompted a "widespread disciplinary revaluation" that has led to a concerted effort to reassess cultural values and "the extension of human morality to the nonhuman world" (Love, 1996:229). The disciplinary revaluation designated to undertake this cultural

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reassessment in literary study is christened “ecocriticism.” With the wave of technological advancement in the name of “development,” caution must be applied before man unconsciously sets the alarm for self-destruction.

According to Adhuze (2017), the environmental perspective to literature started in the latter part of the 20th century in response to the contemporary pressure posed by the natural environment.

The natural environment has been degraded because of man’s exploitative activities with its attendant consequences of earth warming, sea pollution, deforestation, oil spillage, and a host of others. The beauty of nature and the environment have remained a source of literary creativity and integration. Although recent studies have focused on these problems and human beings’ conscious attempts to save the earth from devastation through literary works, this study aims to trace the origin of ecological despoliation to colonialism and expansionism, which began on a large scale in the early modern period of the eighteenth century, as depicted in Daniel Defoe’s *Robinson Crusoe* (1719), and attempts an ecocritical analysis of the text using postcolonial ecocriticism as the theoretical template for the critical analysis. This study analyzes the author’s depiction of nature, the protagonist’s interaction with nature, the connection between the text and the historical period it was set in, and the text’s influence on ecological literacy/consciousness.

The Nature-Culture Controversy

Although human beings cannot be separated from nature, we still have an anthropocentric view of the world that places man at the center of everything. It is undoubtedly clear that human interaction with the environment has a cause and effect on both the human and natural environment. As such, there is a need for humans to be more cautious about how they influence/affect nature.

Expatriating on “the distinction” between nature and culture, Rolston III (1999) quoting Plumwood (1998), reiterates that “nature can be recognized in what has been seen as pure culture, and culture in what has been seen as pure nature,” and as such, the two concepts have a symbiotic relationship. According to Rolston III (1999) this foregrounds Mathew’s (1991) postulation that: “It is no longer controversial to state that a human individual is essentially a cultural being, and that culture is an emanation of Nature” (Rolston III, 1999:154).

In other words, “nature evolved into culture; culture evolved out of nature.” Nature can be independent of culture, but culture is dependent on nature. Without nature, there is no culture; however, nature can exist without culture. Before the advent of industrialization, nature and culture were not considered to be opposite terms. The apparent opposition was recently introduced among Western civilizations. The meaning of “culture” is connected with nature, and being cultural means cultivating lands and hunting or domesticating animals (Williams 1976:87).

At the beginning of the eighteenth century, “culture” took an esthetic meaning, because of artistic and intellectual development (Bate 2000:4). As such, “culture” meant cultivating both the land and oneself through education. By the end of the 19th century, the meaning of “culture” took on another anthropological dimension as an intellectual development of civilization in society (Bate 2000: 4). At the end of the nineteenth century, “culture” took on a sociological connotation that differentiated among social classes (Bate 2000:5).

Buell (2005) opines that “environment” is an anthropocentric term that cannot be taken as being completely synonymous with “nature” because “environment” is sometimes regarded as including not just the physical surroundings but also culture, values, beliefs, and philosophies of a group of people, which has a great influence on the people and their natural environment. As such, the ecocritical perspective in literature focuses on the depiction of the interrelationship between man and the natural environment. The human story is incomplete without the interaction of man with other species, both human and nonhuman, found in his natural habitat.

Theoretical Framework: Postcolonial Ecocriticism

Postcolonialism is a critical term used to mark the end of colonialism and a critical method that can be applied to

any historical period to investigate the effects of colonialism on the world. Postcolonial ecocriticism investigates the effects of colonialism not only on the people but also on the natural environment, where the colonizers treated both the natives and the land as mere objects.

Postcolonial ecocriticism performs the function of advocacy for the transformation of the real world. It challenges hegemonic centrism, which is accountable for an entrenched speciesism that promotes the exploitation of animals and animalized human “others,” a practice “that is at least a couple of millennial old” (Huggan and Tiffin, 2010: p. 8). According to Plumwood, the compartmentalized definition of human into “civilized” and “uncivilized” forms the basis for the colonization of non-European lands and the people and animals that inhabited them as “spaces,” unused, underused, or empty (2003: p. 53). The Western culture of technological advancement regards nature as a commodity, product, resource, and oil in the wheel of “progress”. This conceited ego of the so-called civilized world has silenced “the uncounted voices of nature,” resulting in this ecological crisis. Western civilization has led most people to believe that nature is silent and could be easily exploited (Manes, Meeker, Phillips, 1996).

Graham and Tiffin (2010) argued that postcolonial ecocriticism seeks a redress of the injustices of colonialism in terms of the human, animal, and environment. Postcolonial ecocriticism connects environmental degradation to some ruinous practices of colonialism.

Crusoe’s Anthropocentrism and Domination of the Environment

From the opening chapters of the novel, Crusoe treats nature as a resource to be mastered. Stranded on the island, Crusoe immediately begins shaping the environment to suit human purposes by creating shelter, domesticating goats, planting crops, and altering the landscape for survival. Crusoe’s actions reflect a deeply anthropocentric worldview in which nature exists to serve human ends. This dynamic aligns with scholarly critiques that highlight Crusoe as embodying human domination over nature and colonial logic.

Ecocritics have noted that Crusoe’s attitudes echoes what Crosby (1986) terms “ecological imperialism”, whereby European species and practices displace and reshape environments in the service of human interests. The presence of European fauna—goats, cats, etc.—suggests this early form of ecological transformation on Crusoe’s island.

Island as a motif in literature has been a source of literary imagination in folklore and myths exemplified by Dante’s “The Mountains of Purgatory” in *The Divine Comedy*, William Shakespeare’s mysterious island in *The Tempest*. (Meeker 2011:198-199), and other literary works from the classical times to the present age. The islands provide a picture of peace, isolation, Edenic abundance, and beauty. According to Lowenthal (2007), an island is an exotic reality that is separate from everyday life. A natural site that conjures up a wide variety of images: peace, tranquility, sun, cloudless sky, and crystal sea (Page 208: 2007). It is a positive alternative to modernity and progress, a communal place that celebrates simplicity and collaboration with nature.

The natural concept of the island has a history of colonialism. The island as a setting in literature is a place depicted as a vault of treasure and a battlefield for the supremacy of territorial claim over land and people. It was also created as a haven or site of great upheaval for shipwrecked sailors, as found in Defoe’s *Robinson Crusoe* and Swift’s *Gulliver’s Travels* during the Enlightenment period of the eighteenth century. Sojourning on an island brings the true identity of a character to the fore as the environment pushes them to reveal their true nature, either good or bad. It is a chaotic and violent site because of the scrambling for treasure and trade that often occurs there. The shipwreck and island motifs are temporally and universally connected to a symbolic derangement that threatens the individual’s stability. The utopic scenery often degenerates into a heterotopia in which characters face chaos and disorder and fight each other, as depicted in Crusoe’s enslavement by the Salle Moor pirates:

I fell into terrible misfortunes in this voyage; and the first was this, viz.our ship making her course toward the Canary Island...was surprised in the gray of the morning, by a Turkish rover of Salle,...our ship being disabled, and three of our men killed, and eight wounded, we were obliged to yield, and were carried'd all prisoners into Salle, a port belonging to the Moors, (Defoe 2003:16-17).

Colonialism has a deep impact on the islands that have been influenced by European politics. Colonialists have largely altered the ecosystem by taking forests and minerals elsewhere and by introducing new species of plants and animals (Meeker 2011:201). The biology of many islands has been altered through colonial European exploitation.

Creation of Territories and Enclosures

The new politics of land enclosure had a “destructive impact” on the land (Marzec 2007:8).

This movement marked a change in the economic system from immediate short-term use production to long-term storage production-for-profit (2007:9).

The movement introduced the geographical metaphors of land as “territory,” “field,” and “landscape.” This can be noted in Defoe’s *Robinson Crusoe*, as the eponymous protagonist proudly marks his territory on the deserted island by referring to himself as the “lord of the manor” and “governor of the island.”

In *Robinson Crusoe*’s attempt to overcome his dread of the wild and uncultivated island he is suddenly thrown into, he creates a series of enclosures to turn the land into an object he could easily master. English novels of the eighteenth to twentieth centuries contain numerous references to enclosures as a “new imperial formation of the land” (Marzec 2007:3). In English literature, the land has been characterized as a volatile good that needs to be conquered by the West (Marzec 2007:7).

According to Mentz, “in our age of ecological crisis, the ancient story of shipwreck seems especially topical” (2013:76), adding that *Crusoe*’s arrival at the island can be read as an allegory of human response to ecological crisis, where the action of swimming represents a way of responding to ecological catastrophe (2013:79). The sea is often associated with danger and uncertainty, as found in most Enlightenment novels, e.g., *Gulliver’s Travels* and *Robinson Crusoe*. *Crusoe* chooses to face the hostility of the environment headlong to attain his desire to move to the “upper part of mankind.”

Crusoe experiences two oceanic storms; the second one puts his “human knowledge” of the workings of the storm to task as vividly narrated thus:

A violent tournado or hurricane took us quite out of our knowledge... it blew in such a terrible manner, that for 12 days together we could do nothing but drive, and scudding away before it, let it carry us whither ever fate and the fury of the winds directed... (2003:34-35).

The storm reverses anthropocentrism in the sense that the individual loses control over what surrounds him along with all expectations for the future (Mentz 2013:77). The ocean and the island are symbols of isolation where an individual is left to fight for survival by deploying his own wits in achieving this:

Nothing can describe the confusion of thought which I felt when I sunk into the water; for tho’ I swam very well, yet I could not deliver myself from the waves so as draw breath, until that wave having driven me, or rather carried me a vast way on toward the shore, and having spent itself, went back, and left me upon the land almost dry, but half-dead with the water I took in (2003:37).

Crusoe describes the sea as a hostile force far more powerful than himself, an enormously angry enemy that is going to destroy him. To survive, he has to adapt to the rule of the surging ocean by balancing his swimming abilities to the violent waves of the sea.

According to Smit-Marais, Crusoe's occupation of the island is depicted in his "appropriation" and "domestication" of the island (2011:103). The lack of enclosure on the wild island terrifies Crusoe, so he must quickly create an enclosure to protect himself from any form of attacks by the nonhuman species of the island. He chooses not to inhabit "the land on its own terms" (Marzec 2007:2) by sleeping on a tree the first night he spends on the island. Subsequently, he begins to build a series of enclosures to demarcate his territory and protect himself from any intruder. His description of the island and its vegetation was influenced by his Western social beliefs and ideology. Crusoe sees the island as an empty space that needs to be filled and modeled by Western superiority:

I descended a little on the side of that delicious vale, surveying it with a secret kind of pleasure, ...to think that this was all my own, that I was king and lord of all this country indefeasible, and had a right of possession; ...as any lord of a manor in England (Defoe 2003:80).

Crusoe exerts his dominance on the island by using his cultural tools to control the natural environment he finds himself in. This is achieved by salvaging as many tools and objects as possible from the wrecked ship. On his list of priorities are food, tools to create a suitable environment for himself, ammunition for defense, and food hunting. The accidental growth of barley on the island is attributed to an act of Providence "that God had miraculously caus'd ...for [his] sustenance, on that wild miserable place." This discovery marks the beginning of Crusoe's religious commitment, and he "begins an extended search for the metaphysical cause that would redeem the island and its land" (Marzec 2007:16). Crusoe's discovery of the growth of barley on the island led him to cultivate the land following "the nature of things" or "a divine order" to form society, thus leading to the evolution of the meaning of "culture" as "the intention and practice of 'gardening' as a method of ruling society" (Bauman, quoted by Vandermeersche-Soetaer 2012:16).

The dialectic of possession and responsibility from Christian tradition as argued by Lynn White (1996) based on the pronouncement attributed to God in Genesis 1:26-28, Crusoe embodies the dialectical ideology of possession and responsibility typical of the Christian tradition as he initially "cultivates with a sense of stewardship," transforming the wilderness into a British garden (Scott 2014:646) before his imperialistic instinct took over by colonizing the place and the people he kept as his farmhands, turning it into his plantation for profit. He also engages in the domestication and rearing of animals, leading to the creation of more enclosures to assert his domination of the territory. He is surrounded by a court of animals as the "king" of the island, as reflected in this passage:

It would have made a Stoick smile to have seen me and my little family sit down to dinner; there was my majesty the prince, and lord of the whole island; I had the lives of all y subjects at my absolute command. I could hang, draw, give liberty, and take it away, and no rebels among all my subjects (Defoe 2003:118).

Imperialistic tendencies of the Crusoe

The discovery of a footprint on the island becomes a cause for concern as Crusoe feels threatened and worried about his survival and possession of the island. Before this incident, he wanted to bring civilization to the island by restraining the wild nature as much as possible. After the discovery, he uses the natural wilderness as a means of fortification, meant to hide the civilized enclosures he has built to prevent any invasion from an intruder, as

succinctly described by Smit-Marais (2011): “The looming fear of incursion therefore turns his beloved island from a place of emotional and psychological refuge into a mere fortress.” (112)

The unidentified footprint signifies the activities of the cannibals on the island from which Friday is rescued, and his father’s deliverance coming later. With Friday, the power of the enclosure is re-established. Just as there is no attempt by Crusoe to fully inhabit the island by establishing a connection through a real encounter, there is also no real encounter between Crusoe and Friday as he always puts himself in a detached superior position without ever establishing a true connection (Marzec 2007:18).

With the arrival of Friday on the scene, Crusoe is able to create the ultimate form of space conversion: the establishment of a colony:

My island was now peopled, and I thought I was very rich in subjects. It was a merry reflection that I frequently made, how like a king I looked. First, the whole country was my own meer property, so I had an undoubted right of dominion. Second, my people were perfectly subjected: I was an absolute lord and a law-giver; they all owe their lives to me and were ready to lay down their lives for me if there had been an occasion of it (Defoe 2003: 190).

Crusoe, Sustainability, and Environmental Justice

While Crusoe fashions a domestic environment, his practices often disregard ecological balance. The colonial mindset embedded in his survival strategies replicates broader patterns of resource extraction and environmental exploitation that have long-term consequences. Recent readings such as Sandler and Pezzullo’s *Environmental Justice and Environmentalism* (2007) and AlGhufaili and AlGhufaili (2025) connect Crusoe’s actions to environmental justice themes, arguing that the novel implicitly critiques an anthropocentric worldview that overlooks sustainability and biodiversity.

Crusoe’s focus on human comfort and security overshadows any ethical engagement with the nonhuman communities on the island. Thus, the narrative becomes a site for reflecting on how human survival might be reimagined in harmony with ecological interdependence rather than domination.

Conclusion

An ecocritical reading of *Robinson Crusoe* reveals the novel as a text deeply concerned with the nature of human-environment relations. While Crusoe’s initial domination of the island reflects early modern anthropocentrism and colonial logic, his evolving engagement with nature opens space for ecological reflection. Despite Crusoe’s attempt to domesticate the island and assert his authority, his power does not entirely come from himself, as he is only fortunate to obtain the “cooperation of the land and his subjects.” Thus, the land could be considered a character that plays a significant role in the plot of the story. Crusoe can only be described as an imperialist as the mutineers left behind on the island still carry out Crusoe’s instruction to cultivate and populate the island. However, Crusoe’s authority can be undermined by the force of nature through a natural catastrophe that is more powerful than him. Thus, *Robinson Crusoe* anticipates contemporary environmental concerns and underscores the capacity of the literature to critique and refigure humanity’s place in the more-than-human world.

Consequently, Crusoe’s unplanned sojourn on the island is a warning against an unbridled ambition to amass wealth through the unmindful exploitation of natural resources by man, which has brought humanity to the threshold of ecological crisis that could spell doom for the human species if nothing is done to curb the irrational anthropogenic activities on earth. Like Crusoe, the human species is on the threshold of being lost if they refuse to listen to the natural environment’s ecological warnings.

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